

IMPORTANCE OF MULTI-MEDIA APPROACH IN TEACHING- LEARNING SITUATION FOR THE ATTAINMENT OF EDUCATIONAL GOALS IN THE UBE PROGRAMME IN NIGERIA

By

BABARINDE, R. S.

*Curriculum Studies and Educational Technology Department,
Kwara State College of Education, Ilorin.*

Abstract

The paper discussed the importance of multi-media approach in teaching and learning for the attainment of secondary education goals in Nigeria. It has been used as an aspect of development in Nigeria for the attainment of the national goals. Educational media describe electronic means which contribute immensely in the attainment of various educational patterns in the society. Today, the use of multi-media approach is an aspect of educational technology that concerns the utilization of materials and equipment in solving educational problems in order to achieve various educational goals at all levels. It further discussed educational media, multi-media approach to instruction using the Nigerian experience and remedy to problems of media approach in teaching-learning in various institutions purposely to create quality education. Conclusion was made as to how important the uses of multi-media are with various educational recommendations that could be applied.

Keywords: *Multi-media, Approach, Teaching / Learning Educational Goals, UBE Programmes*

Introduction

Learning is relatively a permanent change in behaviour evidenced by a change in performance through practice, training or experience. Learning is a construct that cannot be seen or measured directly but through an intervening variable such as performance. When there is a change in behaviour, it is then that we can infer that teaching-learning has been effectively achieved or otherwise.

Fakomogbon (2006) describes educational technology from three main perspectives;- Teaching machines and equipment, still projector, tape recorder, computers, slide programmes, overhead projects (other mechanical instructional materials technology is regarded as an assembly of technical materials and resources for educational purposes. In other words, they are referred to as technology in education.

From mass communication system point of view, educational broadcasting, involves educational radio, television, satellites and cable television used in educating a large number of people for use in the schools and society. It is in line with this that Babarinde (2006) and Ajelabi (2005) categorize all educational media under one of the following items;

- i. Audio- Media- which involves teaching and learning devices that appeal to the sense of hearing.
- ii. Visual media; they involve teaching and learning devices that mostly appeal to human senses
- iii. Audio- visual media- refers to those instructional materials that provide the learners with the greatest opportunity of seeing and hearing at the same time.

It is against this background that Babarinde (2006) and Ajelabi (2008) explain the role of teaching and learning as great effect in the society. Others perceived educational technology as a psychological research laboratory where experiments are conducted on learning within closed doors using ideal conditions of learning on human beings and animals, thus, restricting educational technology to the application of certain psychological models or principles under ideal learning conditions.

Topology of Education Technology

Source- Agun and Imogje (1999)

Indeed, virtually all these are the different aspects of educational technology because each one focuses on different materials, on inputs and processes that could help solve educational problems. Consequently, today, educational technology is a problem solving approach in educational technology or education and technology in solving educational problems. The attainment of educational goals and objectives however depends on the quality of instruction given to the learners at a particular level. However, the instructional system component need to be planned, designed, structured and appropriately organized in such a way that the learners who are the focus will benefit thoroughly, purposefully and meaningfully in order that learning is adequately acquired from the schooling system. This could also be achieved by creating an enabling environment that is stimulating to the learner's natural gateways to learning (the sensory organs) in which learning progresses is being carried out for the learners.

Concept of Education Media

Educational media is born of the communication revolution which can be used for instructional process alongside with the teacher, textbook and blackboard. The association further indicates that educational media are also self supporting devices that can present a complete body of information in the teaching-learning process. Agun (1999) and Abolade (2009) defines

complete body of information in the teaching-learning process. Agun (1988) and Abolade (2009) define educational media thus:

Materials that can be used to record, store, preserve and transmit or retrieve information. Teachers and learners can refer to and use them as source to obtain knowledge, new idea and to acquire new skills and competencies. Teacher can also use them to present learning tasks.

When properly used; they can help to make the message of the teachers more valid, interesting and intelligible

Akude (2005) is of the view that all forms of communication through which teaching and learning facilitated are referred to as educational media. Educational media have also been referred to by different authors in the modern society. For instance, Farrant (1980) and Onyejemezi (2008) referred to them as educational resources, curriculum materials, teaching materials, learning materials and educational media respectively, while Babalola (2004) refer to it as resource materials. (others also refer to it as audio-visual materials, educational resources, instructional resources and even curriculum materials).

From this perspective educational media are materials or equipment the teachers use to stimulate the learners through various natural sensory gateways to enable a purposeful and meaningful learning to take place. Qualitative and worth-while education is that which leads to the attainment of the set educational goals, through effectiveness in teaching. No matter the classification of these media, it is not to lose sight of the purpose (i.e instructional objectives) for which such media is being used (Onyejemezi, 2008). Also, Ajayi (2000) practically explained that multi-media are the application of different media in the society to make communication a reality to either by the teacher, textbooks, radio, television and other means of communicative devices in the adult classes.

Multi-Media Approach to Instruction

Globally, in the teaching and learning process, the teacher focuses on ensuring that purposeful and meaningful learning takes place thereby enhancing the quality of teaching. Farrant (1980) asserts that education should make one become a functional product in the society while Peters (1987) explains that education must make one have a relative change in behaviours. Thus, the teacher does through effective utilization of different types of resource media which could be combined or used in isolation. Jonathan (2000) also explains that multimedia has to do with sequential and integrated use of a variety of instructional media, either for presentation to groups or for independent study by students. Example of multimedia is the use of overhead transparency and motion picture with slides for classroom presentation. It may also involve the use of chart, audio cassette recording and a filmstrip for the achievement of a set of objectives for a topic for different uses.

Multimedia therefore means 'multiple media' or 'combination of media'. The media can be still pictures, sound, motion video, animation and or text items combined in a product whose purpose is to communicate information effectively.

Some researchers posited that multimedia is a combination of media that appeal to more than one or two sensory channel (hearing, seeing, feeling) in the teaching and learning process to achieve the anticipated stated objectives of learning on the learners.

Soetan (2007) asserts that instruction is to teacher as learning is to pupil/students. Therefore, multimedia approach to instruction is when that teacher applies varieties of media that appeal to more than one human sense with the aim of facilitating change in the learners' behavior. Multimedia learning relates to a well planned interaction between the learner and the learning activities which are designed in utilizing varieties of media for

learning activities which are designed in utilizing varieties of media for independent study content with those learning kits, self instructional packages to achieve stated specific objectives of a particular content and unit of topic. Multimedia could therefore imply materials or resources, examples of multi media kits are variously available and could be used for individualized institution, small group initiation, large group and even distance learning used to teach an individual, a small group or a large class size.

The Application of Multi-media in Universal Basic Education Programmes

UBE-Is the Universal Basic Education which is a type of education system/pattern being adopted in Nigeria

The objectives of U.B.E Programme in Nigeria are to

1. Prepare the children for life
2. Be able to lay the ground work for sound education
3. Education be free, accessible for all (Education for All)
4. Good preparation for life
5. Inculcation of permanent literacy across board.

UBE Programmes in Nigeria encompass the lower primary, middle primary and upper primary schools (lower basic, middle basic and upper basic JSS 1 – 3). Its curriculum involves reading, writing and numeracy, social studies, civic education, computer education, maths in JSS classes. The methods of approach must incorporate varieties with simple and well illustrated samples due to their ages (Ife, 2008).

In Universal Basic Education schools, the learners' natural gateways to be stimulated for purposeful and meaningful learning to take place. The secondary school learner has come to school to be able to attain the

educational goals and to attain a desirable change in behavior. The implementation of the education policy to achieve the goals and values of education among others things by the government is the approval of utilization of modern educational techniques to improve upon at all levels of education system in order to yield quality.

Also, the National Policy on Education defines U. B. E, as education children receive after primary education and before tertiary stage. Students should offer subjects that are grouped under core, vocational electives and non-prevocational electives at both the junior and senior secondary school levels.

Secondary education prepares the learner for tertiary level and at the same time, gets the recipient ready to function effectively in the community through being self-reliant and acquiring education for shared responsibility. Instruction at the secondary school level needs to be effectively and adequately facilitated for positive attainment of the secondary education goals. Facilitation of instruction according to Ofform (1996), is an important aspect of curriculum planning and implementation which has to do with enhancement of teaching and learning activities. He observes that such:

Learning has been found to be optimally enhanced by adequate and appropriate selection and use of instructional materials by the teacher and the learner as well. It is therefore very essential that teachers are acquainted with the knowledge with which to select and use learning resources effectively for the attainment of set goals (Ofform p. 172).

It is pertinent therefore to admit that effective facilitation of instruction should involve the use of varieties of educational media/device, multimediated techniques by both the teacher and learner for successful and maximal achievement of specific objectives of the lesson contents. The

learners' effective interactions with these media lead to attainment of both general goals of education and specific objectives of the lesson it is used for.

Virtually, no two individuals are the same and that is why there are different ways and styles individuals learn. Effective and efficient teaching and learning take place with a condition. This condition simply means subjecting a learner to materials, objects, equipment (instructional media) for learning to take place. The secondary school learner needs to be provided with such. Multimedia play vital roles in learning because, it attracts more than one sensory channels.

Previous research findings have revealed that in spite of the benefits in the use of multimedia, their use in Nigeria schools are at its low ebb. Onyejemezi (2008). Ajayi (2000) revealed that instructional materials were poorly utilized amongst secondary school teachers in Imo, Kwara, Sokoto, Enugu and Benue States. Ife (2008) carried out a study on the availability, adequacy and utilization of human and materials in the learning of science at the primary school level and found out that only graphic materials, models and some graphic display boards were available in public primary schools in Imo State. The same result is not far from the public secondary schools. There were no projectors nor audio-visuals. Multimedia to carry the content of instruction are ignored hence, the persistent human to human teaching still prevails in our secondary schools. Nwoji (2000) conducted an experimental study to compare the effectiveness of videotaped instruction (VTI) and Audiotape Instruction (ATI) in the teaching of introductory technology topics for JSS 1 students in Nsukka Urban Education zone of Enugu State. The VTI group had a mean score of 14.07 while the ATI group obtained a mean score of 9.08.

Adam (2001), also taught Agricultural Science with videotaped lessons to SS3 students in Ilorin metropolis in Kwara State and found out that videotaped lesson could supplement face-to-face approach in teaching and

learning of Agricultural science and any other subjects.

Importance of learning is realized through learning materials.

Actually, there are research findings, yet it is a truism that these materials are not found in our public institutions due to non-accessibility of materials to teach, lack of needed skills to manipulate these gadget for learning, financial constraints, lack of resourcefulness and above all, proactive inhibition on the part of teachers who find it difficult to accept teaching in a technology –based environment. Thus, dubbing of old notes and talk-chalk approach are still in vogue at all the levels of our educational system. However, the use and current educational development has greatly over come these obstacles worldwide and especially in Nigeria.

Application of multimedia uses and way forward.

Media-mix helps the learner to consolidate what is learnt and the benefits of such approach to instruction needs to be harnessed for factual and better learning to take place at the secondary school level. Unfortunately, such media are virtually lacking in public schools. Hence, the following steps are proffered.

1. Educational Resources Centres (ERC) at the Federal, State and Local Government levels should from time to time produce and store these materials for secondary schools to borrow them.
2. National Association for Education and Media Technology (NAEMT) should organize workshops and Education media exhibitions for teachers to sensitize them on some of these materials and at the same time, learn how to manipulate such materials.
3. Curriculum planners should ensure that multimedia be included as curriculum materials to be used either in combination or in isolation in the teaching and learning process at the secondary school level.

4. National Educational Technology Centre (NETC) that is now attached to the National Open University of Nigeria (NOUN) should be revitalized to enable them carry out effectively the design and production of instructional materials (multi-media inclusive) for secondary school subjects.
5. The educational services of the National Policy on Education should be attended to and provided adequately to meet the felt-needs of the people.
6. Man-power should be put into adequate position in our education system while funds must be made available for the implementation.

Conclusion

Multimedia approach to instruction if effectively selected and utilized, help in attaining a better understanding of the concept taught and more learning experiences would be gained. This paper has succeeded therefore in defining educational media, multimedia and multimedia approach to instruction with reference to research findings that have supported the benefits of multimedia in teaching and learning in Nigerian societies.

Recommendations

- Computer literacy education should be made compulsory for all.
- Man-power to be put in proper place.
- Computer machines should be made available in all schools.
- Teachers in both primary and U.B.E schools must be made to learn computer education.
- Learning materials should be provided for both the teachers and learners.
- The Nigeria national goals on education as stated in the NPE (2009) and (2013) should be focused for implementation

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Abstract

This paper examines the issue of managing basic education for national transformation in Nigeria. An attempt was made to examine the implementation process of universal basic education as well as its objectives. Efforts were also made to examine Universal Basic Education and National transformation as well as some of the problems associated with implementation of Universal Basic Education in Nigeria. It was suggested among others that the issue of funding should be properly looked into as this will go a long way in achieving the objectives of the programme, which can also be a measure towards achieving national transformation.

Introduction

As far back as 1948, the United Nations declared that member states should make education free and compulsory, at least at the elementary and primary levels, while serious efforts should be made to increase citizens access to other levels and form of education. As noted by Ogunniyi (2000) the African charter to which Nigeria was a signatory in 1961 at Addis Ababa, reaffirmed the United Nations Organisation declaration and enjoyed its